

OCCAM DMP v1

Version 1

Description

This Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines how data generated in the OCCAM project (Grant Agreement No. 101182044) will be documented, handled, stored, and shared in accordance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). It describes strategies for ethical data management, long-term preservation, and open access, where possible. It will be continuously updated as new datasets are produced and archived. The Data Management Plan (DMP) and associated metadata will be made available under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license.

The underlying datasets will be made available under the Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC0 1.0), unless restrictions apply due to ethical, legal, or commercial considerations. Any such restrictions will be clearly justified in the DMP.

Funder

European Commission | EC

Grant

OCCAM grant no. 101182044
call: HORIZON-CL6-2024-
FARM2FORK-02

Researchers

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Keith Davidson (0000-0001-9269-3227), Isabel Fuentes-Santos (0000-0002-3298-9648), Maria Saura (0000-0002-2744-2840), Adrianus Both (0000-0001-9499-5333), Johanna Stadmark (0000-0002-0591-6240), Freya Robinson (0000-0001-5417-1540), LAURA CARRARESI (0000-0003-0081-6651), Heiðdís Smáradóttir (0009-0001-2228-9330), Jónas Baldursson (0009-0004-3343-7214), Valur N. Gunnlaugsson (0000-0002-2743-332X)

Organizations

Nofima AS

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [OCCAM DMP v1](#)

Description:

This Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines how data generated in the OCCAM project (Grant Agreement No. 101182044) will be documented, handled, stored, and shared in accordance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). It describes strategies for ethical data management, long-term preservation, and open access, where possible. It will be continuously updated as new datasets are produced and archived. The Data Management Plan (DMP) and associated metadata will be made available under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license.

The underlying datasets will be made available under the Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC0 1.0), unless restrictions apply due to ethical, legal, or commercial considerations. Any such restrictions will be clearly justified in the DMP.

Researchers:

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[Piotr Eljasik \(0000-0001-7220-5484\)](#)

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Organizations:

[Nofima AS](#)

Contact: [Jensen Helene \(helene.jensen@nofima.no\)](mailto:helene.jensen@nofima.no)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [European Commission](#) | [EC](#)

Grants: [OCCAM grant no. 101182044](#) call: [HORIZON-CL6-2024-FARM2FORK-02](#)

Project:

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Measurements from the pyrolysis process of salmon sludge

This dataset includes process monitoring data collected during the pyrolysis of salmon sludge in OCCAM Case Study 4. Parameters include temperature, residence time, mass loss, moisture, and salt content measured at various stages of the process. The data provide insight into process control, operational efficiency, and conversion rates for sludge-to-biochar conversion.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

[Research Data](#)

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

[Digital](#)

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

Both re-used and new data

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Sample or specimen data

Also, Experimental data.

1.1.5 What is its format?

.xlsx

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product
- To improve a product

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education
- Industry

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

[https://zenodo.org/communities/horizonoccam/records?
q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest](https://zenodo.org/communities/horizonoccam/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest)

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Measurements from the pyrolysis process of salmon sludge

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

No

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

1000

Euro

Storage

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Valur N. Gunnlaugsson (0000-0002-2743-332X)

b. Jónas Baldursson (0009-0004-3343-7214)

c. Heiðís Smáradóttir (0009-0001-2228-9330)

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Raw material composition of salmon sludge used in pyrolysis experiments

This dataset contains measurements of the composition of salmon sludge used as input to pyrolysis process trials under OCCAM Case Study 4 (Land-based salmon aquaculture). Data were generated and compiled by Matis and Samherji Fiskeldi within WP3.

It includes proximate analyses (moisture, ash, protein, and salt content) and chemical characteristics of raw sludge material collected during process development. These data serve as baseline input for assessing pyrolysis efficiency and nutrient recovery potential.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

New analytical data generated by Matis; complemented with internal reference data from Samherji Fiskeldi's production process.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Sample or specimen data

Also, Experimental data.

1.1.5 What is its format?

.xlsx

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product
- To improve a product

To document feedstock variability, support process optimisation, and provide baseline material characterisation for life cycle and economic analyses in OCCAM.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education
- Industry

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

[https://zenodo.org/communities/horizonoccam/records?
q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest](https://zenodo.org/communities/horizonoccam/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest)

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Measurements during production of salmon sludge

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Long-term access maintained through Zenodo and OCCAM community.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

Samples analysed by Matis analytical laboratory using standard wet chemistry and spectrophotometric methods.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

1000

Euro

Storage

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Valur N. Gunnlaugsson (0000-0002-2743-332X)

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6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Chemical and physical properties of biochar produced from salmon sludge

This dataset contains analytical measurements of biochar samples obtained from salmon sludge pyrolysis trials. Variables include NPK, heavy metals, salinity, pH, density, and water-holding capacity. These data enable evaluation of biochar quality, safety, and reuse potential as a soil or process additive.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

Both re-used and new data

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Sample or specimen data

Also, Experimental data.

1.1.5 What is its format?

.xlsx

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product
- To improve a product

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

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- Decision makers
- Education
- Industry

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/communities/horizonoccam/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Measurements for biochar products

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

1000

Euro

Storage

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

a. Valur N. Gunnlaugsson (0000-0002-2743-332X)

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6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Atmosphere: NORSCOMS WRF

This dataset contains daily meteorological model outputs from the NORSCOMS WRF (Weather Research and Forecasting) system produced by SAMS. The 2 × 2 km (d03) high-resolution atmospheric model covers regional domains associated with the OCCAM project and provides key atmospheric variables such as wind speed, temperature, and pressure.

The dataset is generated through the WRF numerical weather prediction model, driven by boundary conditions from global forecast data. Model outputs are archived and visualised through SAMS's THREDDS data server. Both new data (from operational WRF runs) and re-used input fields are included.

The dataset supports OCCAM modelling and scenario analysis, providing atmospheric forcing for coupled ocean and biogeochemical models (e.g., WESTCOMS, NORSCOMS-FVCOM).

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

The dataset combines newly generated WRF atmospheric simulations (SAMS operational runs) with re-used boundary conditions and re-analysis inputs from global meteorological datasets (e.g., ECMWF).

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Simulation data, Observational data (model forcing)

1.1.5 What is its format?

NetCDF

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

Approximately 360 items per year

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product
- To improve a product

The dataset provides meteorological forcing and validation data for coupled atmosphere–ocean models used in OCCAM. It supports analyses of emission dispersion, air–sea interactions, and regional weather patterns affecting aquaculture and coastal ecosystem

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Generated by SAMS using the WRF (Weather Research and Forecasting) model configured for the NORSCOMS 2 × 2 km domain. The model assimilates global re-

analysis data and forecast products to generate regional atmospheric fields. Archived outputs are served via the SAMS THREDDS catalogue.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Decision makers
- Education

Useful to atmospheric and ocean modellers, environmental scientists, and regional management authorities concerned with marine weather, emissions, and operational oceanography.

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

PURL

https://thredds.sams.ac.uk/thredds/catalog/scoats-wrf/NORSCOMS_WRF/Archive_forecast/netcdf_2025F/catalog.html

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

Metadata are embedded in the NetCDF file headers and standardised following CF conventions; no separate metadata record will be created in OCCAM.

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

SAMS THREDDS Data Server

https://thredds.sams.ac.uk/thredds/catalog/scoats-wrf/NORSCOMS_WRF/Archive_forecast/netcdf_2025F/catalog.html

SAMS hosts the NORSCOMS WRF data through a THREDDS (Thematic Real-time Environmental Distributed Data Services) server, providing controlled access to forecast and archived NetCDF files.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

Details terms of use

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

No

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

NORSCOMS WRF atmospheric model output, d03 2x2 km domain

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Shared

Restricted with API key, apply to SAMS for access.

Why we require an API key

Reliability: helps us manage automated traffic and keep downloads fast for everyone.

Planning: basic usage metrics guide storage and performance improvements.

Access control: protects datasets with licensing or embargo restrictions.

Compliance: supports attribution and acceptable-use requirements.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.2.6 Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset / output.

Browser (no code)

Just click a file link. If prompted, complete the registration form once. The site sets the cookie and your download proceeds.

curl

curl -L \

```
"https://thredds.sams.ac.uk/thredds/fileServer/path/to/file.nc?
api_key=YOUR_API_KEY" -o file.nc
```

Python (requests)

```
import requests
```

```
url = "https://thredds.sams.ac.uk/thredds/fileServer/path/to/file.nc?
api_key=YOUR_API_KEY"
```

```
r = requests.get(url, allow_redirects=True, timeout=60)
```

```
open("file.nc", "wb").write(r.content)
```

<https://thredds.sams.ac.uk/api/guide>

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

This is not a project specific dataset and will be maintained by the organisation for the foreseeable future

API key

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Indefinite

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

Variable naming follows WRF and CF conventions but does not use a formal controlled vocabulary beyond standard model output terms.

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

Generated using the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model, configured for high-resolution coastal domains (2 km grid spacing). Boundary conditions are derived from ECMWF global forecasts.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

SAMS maintains access for partners but does not guarantee public reuse beyond project scope.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

Each NetCDF file includes full provenance (simulation date, domain, version) in its global attributes

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Keith Davidson (0000-0001-9269-3227)

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Sea Surface Temperatures

This dataset provides global, high-resolution sea surface temperature (SST) analyses derived from the GHRSSST Level 4 MUR Global Foundation Sea Surface Temperature Analysis (v4.1) produced by the Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL) NASA as part of the MUR MEaSURES Project.

The dataset combines multi-sensor observations from microwave and infrared satellite instruments (AMSR-E, AMSR-2, MODIS Aqua/Terra, WindSat, AVHRR, and in situ iQuam data), processed with a multiscale optimal interpolation technique using wavelet basis functions on a global 0.01° grid.

It provides both retrospective (four-day latency) and near-real-time (one-day latency) SST fields. The product supports oceanographic research, climate modelling, and applications such as validation and forcing of regional models under the OCCAM project.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

This dataset reuses existing data produced by the JPL NASA MUR MEaSURES Project. It is accessed via the NASA Physical Oceanography Distributed Active Archive Center (PO.DAAC) and incorporated into OCCAM analyses of ocean temperature dynamics.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

Observational data that is derived and compiled

1.1.5 What is its format?

NetCDF-4

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

Approximately 52 items per year

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product
- To improve a product

To obtain, analyse, and share high-resolution SST information for use in ocean and climate studies, including model forcing, calibration, and validation activities within OCCAM. The dataset enables improved assessment of surface heat fluxes and circulation interactions.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The dataset originates from the Group for High Resolution Sea Surface Temperature (GHRSSST) project and is produced at NASA JPL under the MEaSUREs programme. Data are distributed through the PO.DAAC repository, adhering to GHRSSST Data Processing Specification (GDS v2).

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education

The dataset supports scientists, forecasters, and policy makers involved in ocean monitoring, marine resource management, and climate modelling. It is widely used for operational oceanography, validation of coupled models, and long-term SST trend analyses.

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.5067/GHGMR-4FJ04>

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

Metadata are maintained by NASA PO.DAAC; OCCAM will not create additional metadata records.

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

https://deotb6e7tfubr.cloudfront.net/s3-
edaf5da92e0ce48fb61175c28b67e95d/podaac-ops-cumulus-docs.s3.us-
west-2.amazonaws.com/ghrsst/open/docs/GDS20r5.pdf?A-
userid=None&Expires=1761823770&Signature=bCYb4a9bCHPwziABaLPofd-8O
LM-
xDwOOECc~0EluIpyUl1HBX~1nx9Vemz29E2tu-0QGjUx2sVvIHISfuIEmz9IRufd4Z
ggGOBel8rXqjqBOYCrGbSA9h9gjRaCPdwNRV3uMsKqSx3UmHubx4f1a5qYPEsr
5IJ6wT4wOt9BDt5SyIMM9NMaUd-
bjxoUCKNjjzCiFMiVR7IM6IVBCIYtzxC33Pa1pAfyxPHIr1hAE2ZWqQ03A5mJBimFq
RVJ3M-DnMSLKryjwuV-
kMTto4w-2a~IT1Nh36qlGqt~nNMTNaES3qsRg4NZVw9cXM3X27aqz6tnj7nsUJWR
Ij844JIwxiw__&Key-Pair-Id=K39N79Q36XSAU4

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

NASA Physical Oceanography Distributed Active Archive Center (PO.DAAC)

<https://doi.org/10.5067/GHGMR-4FJ04>

PO.DAAC is part of NASA's Earth Science Data System and serves as the main repository for GHRSSST and MUR products. It ensures long-term open access, preservation, and documentation under NASA's data policies.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

GHRSSST Level 4 MUR Global Foundation Sea Surface Temperature Analysis (v4.1)

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Publicly available via NASA PO.DAAC. No embargo or access restriction applies.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Data remain permanently available via PO.DAAC and NASA archives. OCCAM references the dataset but does not host local copies.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

Indefinite

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

No

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Metadata include download URLs, variable definitions, and processing documentation.

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

Uses GHRSSST and Climate and Forecast (CF) standard names for variables.

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

The MUR SST analysis applies multiscale optimal interpolation using wavelet basis functions, integrating satellite and in-situ data. Detailed methods are described in JPL's GHRSSST documentation.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

No

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

Provenance and processing history recorded in NetCDF global metadata attributes ("history", "source").

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

QA/QC follows GHRSSST and NASA PO.DAAC standards, including cross-sensor validation and routine consistency checks.

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Keith Davidson (0000-0001-9269-3227)

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Long-term stewardship is ensured by NASA PO.DAAC and the MEaSURES programme. Data and metadata are preserved in NASA's Earth Science archives.

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Sea Surface Currents

This dataset provides daily averaged residual sea surface current visualizations from a subset of the North Eastern Atlantic Iberia Biscay Ireland (IBI) NEMO model at 1/36° spatial resolution.

The product, IBI36QV6R1, is produced and maintained by Mercator Ocean International (mercator-ocean.fr) and delivered as part of the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS).

The dataset supports OCCAM oceanographic analyses and visualization of circulation patterns used to drive regional hydrodynamic models (e.g., WESTCOMS and NORSCOMS-FVCOM).

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

This dataset reuses existing ocean model output produced and maintained by Mercator Ocean International under the CMEMS programme. SAMS accesses and visualizes the data subset for OCCAM to support hydrodynamic modelling and marine current analysis.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Observational data that for the purpose in this project is being compiled

1.1.5 What is its format?

NetCDF-4

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

Approximately 360 items per year

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product
- To improve a product

To visualize, analyse, and share information on sea surface current dynamics supporting OCCAM modelling activities.

The dataset enables validation and boundary forcing for regional forecast models (WESTCOMS & NORSCOMS-FVCOM) and contributes to improved understanding of surface circulation patterns.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Originates from Mercator Ocean International's IBI36QV6R1 product, a 1/36° NEMO model configuration for the North-Eastern Atlantic (Iberia-Biscay-Ireland).

Data are distributed through the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS).

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers

- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Industry

The dataset supports oceanographers, modellers, and marine managers interested in surface current variability, drift prediction, and regional ecosystem modelling. It is relevant for research, operational oceanography, and coastal management.

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

Handle

CMEMS assigns persistent identifiers to published ocean products. The IBI36QV6R1 dataset is accessible and citable via the CMEMS data portal.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

Metadata are managed and provided through CMEMS; OCCAM will not duplicate them.

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS)

<https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/>

OCEANCOLOUR_ATL_BGC_L4_NRT_009_116/description

Hosted by CMEMS, operated by Mercator Ocean International, providing open and persistent access to marine observation and model data under the European Copernicus framework.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Sea Surface Currents (IBI36QV6R1 subset)

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Freely accessible via CMEMS data portal under open-use terms.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Long-term access ensured through the Copernicus Marine Service, independent of the OCCAM project duration.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

No

Metadata already maintained by CMEMS.

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

Derived from the NEMO ocean circulation model with 1/36° horizontal resolution, forced by CMEMS atmospheric and boundary conditions. Daily-averaged surface residual currents are extracted and visualized.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

Continued access and reuse are guaranteed through CMEMS, not directly managed by OCCAM.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

Provenance tracked through CMEMS product metadata and Mercator Ocean's operational documentation.

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Keith Davidson (0000-0001-9269-3227)

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

Dataset contains only environmental model outputs; no ethical or legal constraints.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Chlorophyll a

This dataset provides satellite-based, daily, gap-free interpolated chlorophyll a concentrations for the Atlantic Ocean. It is produced under the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS) as part of the Atlantic Ocean Colour Bio-Geo-Chemical (L4) product (product ID: OCEANCOLOUR_ATL_BGC_L4_NRT_009_116, version 202311).

The dataset represents bio-geochemical variables derived from multi-sensor satellite ocean-colour observations, including chlorophyll a and size-fractionated phytoplankton groups (micro-, nano-, pico-, diatoms, dinophytes, haptophytes, green algae, prochlorophytes). It is generated by the Copernicus-GlobColour processing chain and provides near-real-time daily coverage at 1 km spatial resolution.

The data support OCCAM analyses of biological productivity, trophic dynamics, and environmental variability in relation to aquaculture and ecosystem sustainability.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

The dataset reuses existing satellite products produced and distributed by Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS). SAMS accesses and integrates the data for OCCAM research on ocean productivity and biogeochemical variability.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

Observational data that is compiled

1.1.5 What is its format?

NetCDF-4

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

Approximately 52 items per year

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product
- To improve a product

To analyse and visualise spatial and temporal variability in surface chlorophyll a concentrations across the Atlantic. The dataset supports ecosystem assessments and the validation of ocean models used within OCCAM.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Produced by Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS) under the Copernicus-GlobColour project. The data combine multiple satellite sensors

and are distributed as the Atlantic Ocean Colour Bio-Geo-Chemical L4 daily product (OCEANCOLOUR_ATL_BGC_L4_NRT_009_116).

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Industry

Relevant for scientists and decision-makers analysing marine primary production, coastal eutrophication, or aquaculture sustainability. It is also useful for public authorities and environmental agencies monitoring ocean health.

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

PURL

https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/OCEANCOLOUR_ATL_BGC_L4_NRT_009_116/description

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

Metadata are fully managed and published by CMEMS; no additional metadata will be created by OCCAM

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS)

https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/OCEANCOLOUR_ATL_BGC_L4_NRT_009_116/description

CMEMS, operated by Mercator Ocean International, provides authoritative European ocean observation and modelling data. It ensures long-term open access, versioning, and quality control for marine bio-geochemical products.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Atlantic Ocean Colour Bio-Geo-Chemical L4 Daily Product
(OCEANCOLOUR_ATL_BGC_L4_NRT_009_116)

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Freely accessible through the CMEMS data portal.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Long-term open access is maintained through CMEMS beyond OCCAM's lifetime.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

No

Already maintained by CMEMS.

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

Uses CMEMS and Climate & Forecast (CF) standard names for variables (e.g., mass_concentration_of_chlorophyll_in_sea_water).

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

Long-term reuse ensured by CMEMS; no additional OCCAM measures required.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

Provenance and processing chain documented in CMEMS product metadata and user guides.

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Keith Davidson (0000-0001-9269-3227)

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Food Standards Scotland biotoxin producing phytoplankton monitoring data

This dataset consists of observational data collected through the Food Standards Scotland (FSS) biotoxin-producing phytoplankton monitoring programme. It includes approximately 1,000 observations per year on phytoplankton species relevant to biotoxin production in Scottish waters. The dataset is maintained by SAMS and Seafood Shetland and made available through the Food Standards Scotland website.

The purpose of the dataset is to obtain and share information on harmful algal blooms (HAB) to support seafood safety monitoring, regulatory compliance, and product development under the OCCAM project framework. The data are openly available and primarily intended for public use, analysis, and reporting on marine biotoxin risks.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

This dataset reuses existing observational data produced and maintained by Food Standards Scotland (FSS) as part of the national biotoxin and phytoplankton monitoring programme. SAMS and Seafood Shetland access and compile these data for the OCCAM project. The data are publicly available via the FSS website and reused to support marine biotoxin risk analysis and seafood safety assessments within the project

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

1.1.5 What is its format?

The dataset is provided in spreadsheet format (.xlsx) containing tabular data on phytoplankton species, abundance, and sampling metadata collected by Food Standards Scotland.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

Approximately 1,000 items (records) per year.

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product
- To improve a product

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The dataset originates from the Food Standards Scotland (FSS) biotoxin-producing phytoplankton monitoring programme. Data are collected by accredited monitoring agencies under FSS oversight and compiled by SAMS and Seafood Shetland for OCCAM. The dataset represents verified, publicly available observations on phytoplankton species relevant to biotoxin production in Scottish coastal waters.

Provenance: Food Standards Scotland → national monitoring programme → SAMS/Seafood Shetland (OCCAM integration).

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Decision makers
- Education
- The public
- Industry

The dataset is useful to researchers studying harmful algal blooms (HAB), food safety, and marine ecosystem dynamics; to policymakers and regulators involved in seafood safety and environmental monitoring; and to seafood producers and processors seeking to manage HAB-related risks. The open availability of these data also benefits the general public and educational users interested in marine health and food security.

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

Metadata are not provided beyond the descriptive context on the Food Standards Scotland website, which includes sampling site details, species

names, and dates. No structured or machine-readable metadata are associated with the dataset.

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Food Standards Scotland (FSS) website

<https://www.foodstandards.gov.scot/business-and-industry/industry-specific-advice/shellfish>

The dataset is hosted by Food Standards Scotland (FSS) as part of its national biotoxin and phytoplankton monitoring programme. The repository provides open public access to data on harmful algal bloom (HAB) species, sampling sites, and temporal variation in Scottish waters. Although the site is not a formal research data repository, it functions as the authoritative national source for seafood safety monitoring data in Scotland.

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Food Standards Scotland biotoxin producing phytoplankton monitoring data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

The dataset is openly available to the public via the Food Standards Scotland website. Users can access and download the data directly without registration or authentication. No embargo or access restrictions apply.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

The dataset will remain accessible through the Food Standards Scotland website, which maintains the long-term archive of national seafood monitoring data. As it is managed externally by FSS, continued access is ensured independently of the OCCAM project timeline.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

No

The dataset is already openly shared through the Food Standards Scotland (FSS) website and does not include separate structured metadata. No additional metadata will be created or maintained within OCCAM.

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

No

The Food Standards Scotland web pages already include direct access information and contextual details about sampling and data content. No separate metadata record exists in a structured repository format.

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

No

The dataset and its descriptive context are maintained by Food Standards Scotland, which ensures continued hosting. If the dataset were to be removed, no independent metadata record would remain under the OCCAM project.

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

Not applicable

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

The dataset will continue to be hosted and maintained by Food Standards Scotland, independent of the OCCAM project. No additional reuse arrangements are required by the consortium, as the dataset's availability and reuse are already ensured by the FSS's open access framework.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

Provenance is clearly established through Food Standards Scotland's official monitoring programme, which provides transparent information about sampling locations, species, and responsible institutions. The dataset includes contextual metadata such as sampling date and geographic area, providing traceability of data collection.

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Keith Davidson (0000-0001-9269-3227)

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

The dataset contains no personal or confidential information. It consists solely of observational records of phytoplankton species and sampling data. There are no ethical or legal restrictions on reuse, and open sharing complies with FSS and OCCAM data policies.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

River volume Eume and Mandeo (CS6)

This dataset compiles daily and monthly river discharge data from the Eume and Mandeo rivers in Galicia, Spain. The data are re-used from official hydrological monitoring stations managed by Meteogalicia and Augas de Galicia, with additional curation and aggregation by CSIC under OCCAM Work Package 1 (Climate analysis for Case Study 6).

The dataset includes CSV-formatted time series of river flow (m³/s), water level, and station metadata. It is used to analyse hydrological variability and freshwater input affecting coastal and estuarine systems in the Galician region. Monthly means are further processed and deposited in Zenodo for integration with OCCAM climate datasets.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

The dataset reuses hydrological data from existing public sources (Meteogalicia, Augas de Galicia, and the Spanish Open Data Portal).

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

1.1.5 What is its format?

CSV

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product
- To improve a product

To obtain and analyse hydrological information supporting OCCAM CS6 climate and ecosystem modelling; to inform process improvement and coupling with marine data products.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data originate from public hydrological monitoring networks managed by Meteogalicia and Augas de Galicia. Official station information and time series are accessed through the agencies' web portals and Spain's national open-data infrastructure.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- The public

- Industry

Useful for hydrologists, environmental modellers, and regional authorities evaluating freshwater fluxes to coastal environments and climate-related variability.

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

a. Meteogalicia and Augas de Galicia open-data portals

<https://sig.miteco.gob.es/redes-seguimiento/>

b. Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/communities/horizonoccam/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Meteogalicia and Augas de Galicia maintain national hydrological data repositories ensuring open access to quality-controlled time-series data. Zenodo is used for archiving derived monthly means with persistent DOIs.

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

River volume Eume and Mandeo (monthly means for OCCAM CS6)

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Data remain publicly available from national portals and in Zenodo after the project concludes.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Yes – through Zenodo and national portals

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Maria Saura (0000-0002-2744-2840)

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

OCCAM Stakeholder Database

This dataset contains a compiled list of stakeholders relevant to the OCCAM project. It includes contact details (names, email addresses, and institutional affiliations), stakeholder categories, and project-specific tagging to facilitate communication, dissemination, and engagement activities within Work Package 6 (Stakeholder interaction and dissemination).

The database is maintained by SUBNet on behalf of the OCCAM consortium and used solely for internal coordination and engagement tracking. It will not be made public.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

The dataset re-uses and updates existing stakeholder contact lists compiled from publicly available sources and prior EU projects, harmonised for OCCAM use.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

To share and coordinate stakeholder information within the OCCAM consortium; to support dissemination, engagement, and impact activities under WP6.

1.1.5 What is its format?

xlsx

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

2MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Compiled by SUBNet from internal project records, partner recommendations, and public institutional information. Maintained and updated throughout the project for stakeholder engagement management.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Researchers

Project partners and communication leads; not intended for external use.

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

Dataset description maintained internally within OCCAM documentation; no public metadata record.

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Internal storage

Dataset stored securely on Nofima's internal server with restricted access following institutional security and GDPR protocols.

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

OCCAM Stakeholder Database

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

The dataset is not shared publicly; access is limited to authorised OCCAM personnel for internal communication and reporting.

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Data retained for audit and reporting purposes until project closure; deleted or anonymised thereafter.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

Internal tagging (e.g., policy, industry, NGO) used for categorisation but not a standard vocabulary.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Archiving

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Freya Robinson (0000-0001-5417-1540)

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Salmon Farming Feeding Rate vs Temperature

The dataset is based on approximately 1.3 million daily observations on feeding and temperature in all Salmon cages at sea in the Faroe Islands from January 2009 to July 2025.

Monthly values are given for: Fishcount (total number of farmed salmon), Average weight (Average weight of all the farmed fish), Temperature (average of all temperature observations at ~5m depth in the cages), Feeding rate SFR (Average Specific Feeding rate for all the farmed fish)

Datasource: Bakkafrost (Fishtalk), Hiddenfjord (Mercatus), Mowi (Meractus)

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

The dataset reuses production data from existing national and industrial sources, harmonised and reformatted for OCCAM CS3 analysis.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

1.1.5 What is its format?

csv

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product
- To improve a product

To obtain and analyse salmon farming production trends and inform case-study analysis within OCCAM CS3.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Derived from publicly available and partner-provided data on salmon aquaculture production in the Faroe Islands. Data aggregation and formatting performed by Avrik.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

- Industry

The dataset supports scientific and applied analyses of production efficiency, sustainability, and innovation in Faroese salmon aquaculture.

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

Metadata will include descriptive, structural and provenance metadata

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

Repository hosted by Zenodo

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Salmon Farming Feeding Rate vs Temperature

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

Access will be limited to OCCAM partners due to sectoral data-sharing agreements.

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Dataset retained by Avrik; archived copy stored in Zenodo with restricted access for internal project use.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Rúni Dam (0009-0006-7329-0987)

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Seawater_PROINSA_Ares_Betanzos

This dataset provides measurements of seawater characteristics at the PROINSA site located in the Ares–Betanzos estuary (Galicia, Spain). It includes observational time-series of temperature, salinity, and related physical and chemical parameters recorded in connection with OCCAM Case Study 6.

The dataset was compiled and quality-checked by CSIC (Isabel Fuentes Santos) within Work Package 1, using data re-used from Meteogalicia and Instituto Español de Oceanografía (IEO) sources. The data are stored in CSV format and used to characterise seawater conditions influencing aquaculture and environmental variability in the study area.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

The dataset reuses existing observational data from Meteogalicia and IEO oceanographic monitoring programmes.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

1.1.5 What is its format?

CSV

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

50MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product
- To improve a product

To obtain and analyse seawater characteristics in the Ares–Betanzos estuary; to inform model calibration and support environmental analyses in OCCAM Case Study 6.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data derived from regional oceanographic monitoring stations and archives managed by Meteogalicia and IEO. The dataset was curated, formatted, and harmonised by CSIC for OCCAM use.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Industry

Useful for environmental scientists, aquaculture stakeholders, and regional managers evaluating estuarine and coastal water dynamics.

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

The dataset is re-used and compiled from national sources; no persistent identifier is assigned. Metadata reference included in Deliverable D1.1 (Zenodo DOI).

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

Metadata summary is available in Deliverable D1.1_OCCAM_CS6_Climate data.xlsx (Zenodo DOI when uploaded), which documents parameter definitions, units, and data sources.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/communities/horizonoccam/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

dataset re-used internally for OCCAM; original sources remain publicly accessible through Meteogalicia and IEO.

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Isabel Fuentes-Santos (0000-0002-3298-9648)

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Coastal winds SIMAR_3007036 (Ares–Betanzos, Galicia, Spain)

This dataset provides coastal wind data for the Ares–Betanzos estuary in Galicia (Spain), re-used from the SIMAR_3007036 hindcast series produced by Puertos del Estado (Spanish Ports Authority).

It contains simulated daily and monthly wind variables, including wind speed and direction at 10 m height, generated from the SIMAR ocean–atmosphere model. The dataset was curated by CSIC (Isabel Fuentes Santos) within Work Package 1 of the OCCAM project.

The data are used to describe and analyse the wind forcing conditions that influence regional hydrodynamics and aquaculture performance under Case Study 6.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

Data re-used from Puertos del Estado's SIMAR hindcast model database (<https://portus.puertos.es>)

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Simulation

1.1.5 What is its format?

csv

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

50MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information

To obtain wind forcing information for coastal and estuarine modelling, support environmental analysis, and improve process coupling within OCCAM Case Study 6.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data originate from Puertos del Estado's SIMAR model (hindcast product 3007036), which provides gridded time series of simulated marine meteorological parameters. Data were accessed through the PORTUS platform and processed by CSIC for monthly aggregation.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Industry

Useful for environmental and ocean modellers, aquaculture operators, and coastal planners analysing local wind forcing and its variability.

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

DOI (Zenodo)

Monthly mean subset deposited in Zenodo with DOI; full-resolution data available from Puertos del Estado via the PORTUS platform.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

Metadata summary included in Deliverable D1.1_OCCAM_CS6_Climate data.xlsx (Zenodo DOI), referencing model configuration and parameter definitions.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

a. Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/communities/horizonoccam/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

b. Puertos del Estado – PORTUS platform

<https://portus.puertos.es/#/>

Puertos del Estado provides official marine hindcast datasets for Spain. The derived OCCAM subset is archived in Zenodo with persistent DOI and descriptive metadata.

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Coastal winds SIMAR_3007036 (Ares–Betanzos, CS6)

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

Data remain accessible through Puertos del Estado (PORTUS platform) and Zenodo after OCCAM ends.

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Infrastructure Grant

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Isabel Fuentes-Santos (0000-0002-3298-9648)

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Meteorological data_CS2

This dataset contains meteorological data collected from four observation stations in Galicia, Spain: A Gándara, Cee, Camariñas, and Lira. The dataset includes time-series measurements of air temperature, wind speed and direction, humidity, precipitation, and atmospheric pressure.

The data originate from Meteogalicia's meteorological network and have been curated and aggregated by CSIC (María Saura) within OCCAM Work Package 1, under Case Study 2.

Monthly mean values are calculated for integration with other climate datasets in OCCAM and archived in Zenodo.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

Re-used from Meteogalicia's public meteorological station data, curated and aggregated by CSIC for OCCAM CS2.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

1.1.5 What is its format?

csv

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

5MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product
- To improve a product

To obtain and analyse meteorological conditions relevant to coastal aquaculture systems in OCCAM CS2; to inform environmental modelling, emission estimates, and process improvements.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data originate from Meteogalicia's public meteorological stations, following the agency's data collection protocols and device calibration standards.

Station details and technical documentation are available at:

<https://www.meteogalicia.gal/web/observacion/rede-meteorologica>

Protocol: recollida_de_datos_es.pdf

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Industry

Relevant for environmental modellers and researchers assessing meteorological variability, climate forcing, and aquaculture site performance.

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

DOI (Zenodo, for aggregated monthly dataset)

Monthly mean dataset deposited in Zenodo with DOI; full-resolution data available from Meteogalicia's open portal.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

a. Meteogalicia

<https://www.meteogalicia.gal/web/observacion/rede-meteorologica>

Meteogalicia is the regional meteorological service of Galicia, providing open access to quality-controlled meteorological data. Zenodo ensures long-term open access to aggregated versions within the OCCAM community.

b. Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/communities/horizonoccam/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Meteorological data_CS2

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Remains available indefinitely through Meteogalicia and Zenodo.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

Yes – in D1.1_OCCAM_CS2_Climate data.xlsx (Zenodo DOI when added).

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes – includes links to original datasets and documentation.

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Yes – data openly available through Meteogalicia and Zenodo.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes – in D1.1_OCCAM_CS2_Climate data.xlsx and station metadata.

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Maria Saura (0000-0002-2744-2840)

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

River volume Castro (CS2)

This dataset compiles daily and monthly river discharge data from the Castro river (Galicia, Spain), re-used from public hydrological networks managed by Meteogalicia and Augas de Galicia.

It includes time-series of river flow (m³/s) and water level, together with station metadata from the official monitoring network. The dataset was curated and harmonised by CSIC (María Saura) under Work Package 1 for OCCAM Case Study 2, and monthly means are deposited in Zenodo for open access.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

Data re-used from national hydrological networks and public monitoring stations operated by Meteogalicia and Augas de Galicia.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

1.1.5 What is its format?

csv

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product
- To improve a product

To obtain and analyse hydrological data for OCCAM Case Study 2; to support climate and environmental analyses of aquaculture-relevant watersheds.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data originate from the official hydrological station network managed by Meteogalicia and Augas de Galicia.

Detailed information on measurement methods and station metadata is available through:

Meteogalicia stations portal

<https://servizos.meteogalicia.gal/mgafos/estacions/estacions.action#>

Spanish National Water Information System (MITECO)

<https://sig.miteco.gob.es/redes-seguimiento/>

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

Supports hydrological and environmental modelling, climate variability studies, and sustainability assessments in OCCAM Case Study 2.

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

DOI (Zenodo)

Monthly means deposited in Zenodo under the OCCAM community (DOI assigned upon upload).

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

Metadata summary available in Deliverable D1.1_OCCAM_CS2_Climate data.xlsx (Zenodo DOI), documenting stations, parameters, and data provenance.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

a. Meteogalicia, Spanish Government Open Data Portal (MITECO)

https://servizos.meteogalicia.gal/mgafos/estacions/estacions.action?request_locale=gl#

<https://sig.miteco.gob.es/redes-seguimiento/>

Meteogalicia and Augas de Galicia ensure long-term open access and quality-controlled hydrological data. Zenodo provides DOI-based archiving for derived monthly datasets within OCCAM.

b. Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/communities/horizonoccam/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

River volume Castro (CS2)

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Data remain publicly accessible via Meteogalicia, MITECO, and Zenodo after project completion.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

Data collected using standard hydrological monitoring methods by Meteogalicia and Augas de Galicia; processed and monthly aggregated by CSIC for OCCAM.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Yes – data remain open via national repositories and Zenodo.

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Maria Saura (0000-0002-2744-2840)

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Coastal winds SIMAR_3007024_Lires

This dataset provides coastal wind data for the Lires coastal area (Galicia, Spain), derived from the SIMAR_3007024 hindcast model produced by Puertos del Estado (Spanish Ports Authority).

It contains daily and monthly time-series of wind speed and direction (10 m height) based on the SIMAR ocean-atmosphere model. Data were extracted, processed, and aggregated by CSIC (María Saura) under Work Package 1 (Climate analysis) in the OCCAM project (Case Study 2).

Monthly means are deposited in Zenodo for open access, while the original full-resolution data remain accessible via the PORTUS platform.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

Re-used from the SIMAR hindcast model (Puertos del Estado). Aggregated and reformatted for OCCAM CS2 by CSIC.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Simulation

1.1.5 What is its format?

csv

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

50MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product
- To improve a product

To obtain wind forcing information for coastal and estuarine analyses; to support environmental modelling and aquaculture system studies in OCCAM CS2.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data originate from Puertos del Estado's SIMAR_3007024 hindcast database. Model and validation are documented in:

https://bancodatos.puertos.es/BD/informes/INT_8.pdf.

Data accessed through the PORTUS platform (<https://portus.puertos.es/#/>) and processed by CSIC.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Industry

Useful for environmental and atmospheric modelling, site assessment, and long-term variability analysis.

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI (Zenodo)

Monthly mean subset archived in Zenodo (OCCAM community). Original data identified by Puertos del Estado's SIMAR model code 3007024.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

Metadata described in Deliverable D1.1_OCCAM_CS2_Climate data.xlsx (Zenodo DOI), detailing parameters, temporal coverage, and model configuration.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

a. Puertos del Estado – PORTUS platform

<https://portus.puertos.es/#/>

Puertos del Estado maintains national marine hindcast data. Zenodo ensures long-term archiving and DOI assignment for aggregated subsets.

b. Zenodo – OCCAM Community

<https://zenodo.org/communities/horizonoccam/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Coastal winds SIMAR_3007024_Lires (CS2)

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Remains permanently available through Puertos del Estado and Zenodo.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes – Puertos del Estado INT_8 technical report and metadata sheet in D1.1.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

SIMAR data validated against meteorological buoy observations by Puertos del Estado; secondary QA by CSIC during aggregation.

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Maria Saura (0000-0002-2744-2840)

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Thermohaline_SIMAR_3007024_Lires

This dataset provides thermohaline parameters (temperature and salinity) for the Lires coastal area (Galicia, Spain), derived from the SIMAR_3007024 hindcast model produced by Puertos del Estado (Spanish Ports Authority).

The dataset contains daily and monthly simulated values of seawater temperature and salinity at different depths, extracted from the SIMAR ocean-atmosphere model. It has been processed and aggregated by CSIC (María Saura) under OCCAM Work Package 1, within Case Study 2.

Monthly means are published in Zenodo for open access, while original full-resolution data remain available through the PORTUS platform.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

Re-used from the SIMAR hindcast model by Puertos del Estado, processed for OCCAM CS2 by CSIC.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Simulation

1.1.5 What is its format?

csv

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

50MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product
- To improve a product

To obtain thermohaline information for environmental and aquaculture-related analysis in OCCAM Case Study 2, supporting oceanographic modelling and system assessment.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data derived from Puertos del Estado's SIMAR_3007024 model dataset, which simulates oceanic and atmospheric conditions using coupled numerical models.

Model documentation: INT_8 Technical Report

https://bancodatos.puertos.es/BD/informes/INT_8.pdf

Data accessed via the PORTUS platform: <https://portus.puertos.es/#/>

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers

- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Industry

Useful for climate and environmental analysis, model calibration, and evaluation of thermohaline variability in the coastal environment.

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

DOI (Zenodo)

Monthly mean dataset deposited in Zenodo (OCCAM community). Original data identifiable by SIMAR model code 3007024.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

Metadata described in Deliverable D1.1_OCCAM_CS2_Climate data.xlsx (Zenodo DOI), including parameters, units, and model configurations.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

a. Puertos del Estado – PORTUS platform

<https://portus.puertos.es/#/>

Puertos del Estado manages Spain's national oceanographic and meteorological hindcast datasets. Zenodo ensures long-term archiving and DOI assignment for aggregated OCCAM subsets.

b. Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/communities/horizonoccam/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Thermohaline_SIMAR_3007024_Lires (CS2)

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Yes – open access maintained through Puertos del Estado and Zenodo.

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Maria Saura (0000-0002-2744-2840)

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Meteorological data CIS-FERROL

This dataset includes meteorological time-series data from the CIS-Ferrol station (Galicia, Spain). It provides hourly and daily measurements of air temperature, wind speed and direction, humidity, precipitation, and atmospheric pressure.

The data originate from Meteogalicia's regional meteorological monitoring network and have been re-used and processed by CSIC (Isabel Fuentes Santos) within Work Package 1 of the OCCAM project, specifically for Case Study 6.

The dataset is used to describe atmospheric conditions influencing coastal and aquaculture systems and to support climate analysis and modelling activities.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

Data re-used from Meteogalicia's meteorological network and reformatted for OCCAM use.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

1.1.5 What is its format?

csv

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product
- To improve a product

To obtain meteorological information relevant to environmental and aquaculture assessments; to inform modelling and process improvement within OCCAM Case Study 6.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data originate from Meteogalicia's meteorological station CIS-Ferrol.

Technical details and calibration procedures are available at:

<https://www.meteogalicia.gal/web/observacion/rede-meteorologica>

Data collection protocol:

https://www.meteogalicia.gal/datosred/infoweb/meteo/docs/meteoescolas/documentos/recollida_de_datos_es.pdf

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

Relevant for climate, environmental, and production models assessing site-level meteorological forcing and variability.

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

Monthly mean dataset deposited in Zenodo under OCCAM community (DOI assigned upon upload).

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

Metadata summary available in Deliverable D1.1_OCCAM_CS6_Climate data.xlsx (Zenodo DOI), including parameter definitions and station metadata.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

a. Meteogalicia

<https://www.meteogalicia.gal/web/observacion/rede-meteorologica>

Meteogalicia maintains open-access meteorological datasets following standard QA/QC procedures. Zenodo ensures long-term preservation and DOI assignment for aggregated OCCAM subsets.

b. Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/communities/horizonoccam/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Meteorological data CIS-FERROL (CS6)

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Remains permanently available through Meteogalicia and Zenodo.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Remains permanently available through Meteogalicia and Zenodo.

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Isabel Fuentes-Santos (0000-0002-3298-9648)

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

CSIC adheres to institutional data management and backup procedures; no additional measures required.

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Coastal winds REDEXT_2246

This dataset provides coastal wind data for the Ares–Betanzos area (Galicia, Spain), obtained from the REDEXT_2246 station and the Puertos del Estado database.

It contains observational time-series of wind speed and direction at 10 m height, available as daily and monthly values. The dataset was curated and aggregated by CSIC (Isabel Fuentes Santos) within OCCAM Work Package 1 (Climate analysis) for Case Study 6.

Monthly mean data are published on Zenodo, while original records are publicly available from the PORTUS platform maintained by Puertos del Estado.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

Re-used from Puertos del Estado's REDEXT observational database and reformatted for OCCAM CS6 by CSIC.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

1.1.5 What is its format?

csv

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

50MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product
- To improve a product

To obtain information for environmental and climate analysis, to support aquaculture-related modelling and site assessments under OCCAM CS6.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data originate from Puertos del Estado's REDEXT meteorological network, which provides validated long-term observations at coastal stations.

Documentation: https://bancodatos.puertos.es/BD/informes/INT_2.pdf

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Industry

Supports environmental monitoring, atmospheric modelling, and analysis of wind forcing in the Ares–Betanzos area.

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

Monthly mean dataset deposited in Zenodo (OCCAM community).

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

Metadata summary included in Deliverable D1.1_OCCAM_CS6_Climate data.xlsx (Zenodo DOI).

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

a. Puertos del Estado – PORTUS platform

<https://portus.puertos.es/#/>

Puertos del Estado provides validated meteorological and oceanographic data for Spanish waters. Zenodo ensures FAIR archiving and DOI assignment for project-derived subsets.

b. Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/communities/horizonoccam/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Coastal winds REDEXT_2246 (CS6)

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Data remain available via the Puertos del Estado PORTUS platform and Zenodo after OCCAM completion.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Data remain available via the Puertos del Estado PORTUS platform and Zenodo after OCCAM completion.

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Isabel Fuentes-Santos (0000-0002-3298-9648)

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Business Model Data

This dataset contains qualitative and quantitative data collected and compiled by Nofima under Work Package 7 (Innovation, Business Models, and Exploitation) of the OCCAM project.

It includes structured information on company characteristics, innovation strategies, resource use, and sustainability-related practices across selected partners, sectors, and case studies. The dataset supports analysis of value-chain structures, innovation pathways, and business-model typologies for sustainable aquaculture and circular bioeconomy transitions.

All individual identifiers have been removed; only anonymised and aggregated results are used in OCCAM deliverables and publications.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

1.1.5 What is its format?

xlsx, docx

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

300kb

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Data compiled and analysed by Laura Carraresi (Nofima). Information originates from OCCAM project partners, industry interactions, and secondary documentation.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Industry

Supports evidence-based analysis of innovation dynamics and sustainable business-model development within the aquaculture sector

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

None

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Internal/Nofima encrypted research server

Data stored on Nofima's secure institutional environment (Microsoft Teams, SharePoint-based) with controlled access for authorised personnel only.

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Business Model Data (OCCAM WP7)

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Storage

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

LAURA CARRARESI (0000-0003-0081-6651)

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

yes

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Anonymising data where necessary

We will apply for Sikt approval in Norway to use sensitive data

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

D1.1_OCCAM_CS8_Climate data

The file contains relevant climate data for Case Study 8 of the OCCAM project.

The dataset includes temperature, salinity, air temperature, nutrients (nitrite, nitrate, ammonium, phosphate, phosphorus), Secchi depth, and species information for *Saccharina latissima* and *Ulva fenestrata*.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

1.1.5 What is its format?

xlsx

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

5000kb

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product
- To improve a product

To provide climate and environmental parameters relevant to OCCAM Case Study 8.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Researchers

Scientific and research purposes within OCCAM.

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

Zenodo (when uploaded)

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/communities/horizonoccam/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

D1.1_OCCAM_CS8_Climate_Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

- a. Adrianus Both (0000-0001-9499-5333)
- b. Alice Hedensjö (0009-0007-3864-2657)
- c. Svenja Heß (0009-0007-8174-7147)
- d. Göran Nylund (0000-0002-4087-3207)

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

D1.1_OCCAM_CS7_Climate data

This dataset contains climate-related data from Case Study 7 in the OCCAM project.

The data are in Excel format and include measurements relevant to the study of environmental and operational conditions.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

1.1.5 What is its format?

xlsx

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

5000kb

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product
- To improve a product

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Industry

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

When uploaded to Zenodo

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/communities/horizonoccam/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

D1.1_OCCAM_CS7_Climate data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

- a. Svenja Heß (0009-0007-8174-7147)
 - b. Alice Hedensjö (0009-0007-3864-2657)
 - c. Adrianus Both (0000-0001-9499-5333)
- Christian Vorbeck
- d. Kent Berntsson

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

FarCoast OCCAM CS3

This dataset contains hourly output values from the FarCoast ocean model including velocities, temperature, and salinity.

Metadata describe resolution, time period, and spatial coverage (longitude–latitude).

The dataset is simulation-based and part of Case Study 3 (WP3) of the OCCAM project.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Simulation

1.1.5 What is its format?

Meta data as .yaml data as .netcdf

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

The simulated data is ~1TB the meta data is 10 kb

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To develop a product
- To improve a product

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Decision makers

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- None

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

A technical meta data file with information of resolution, time period, velocities, salinity tempearture and longitude latitude. The data file contains hourly output values from the Farcoast ocean model of velocities, temperature and salinity

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Internal

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

FarCoast OCCAM CS3

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Archiving

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Sissal Erenbjerg (0000-0001-7619-4049)

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Salmon Lice on farmed fish OCCAM CS3

This dataset contains observational data on salmon lice abundance on farmed fish, collected within Case Study 3 of the OCCAM project.

It documents environmental and biological conditions relevant to aquaculture monitoring.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

1.1.5 What is its format?

csv

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

0,5MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To obtain information

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Researchers

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

From Zenodo when uploaded

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

Metadata will include descriptive, structural, and provenance metadata.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

[https://zenodo.org/communities/horizonoccam/records?
q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest](https://zenodo.org/communities/horizonoccam/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest)

Zenodo is an open-access repository operated by CERN under the European OpenAIRE programme. It provides persistent identifiers and long-term storage for research data.

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Salmon Lice on farmed fish OCCAM CS3

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Gunnvør á Norði (0000-0003-1550-6007)

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Faroese Salmon Lice Model OCCAM CS3

This dataset contains code and configuration files for the Faroese salmon lice model developed within Case Study 3 (WP3) of the OCCAM project.

The model includes Python scripts, markdown documentation, and YAML configuration files describing the simulation setup and model parameters.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.5 What is its format?

Python files (.py), Markdown (.md), YAML (.yaml)

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To develop a product

- To improve a product

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

2 Links Between Outputs

3 FAIR Practices

3.1 Making data and other outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Other

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

A README.md file describing the model repository content and how to use the model will be provided.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

GitHub

<https://github.com/Fiskaaling>

GitHub is a code repository platform that supports open sharing of software and documentation.

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Faroese Salmon Lice Model OCCAM CS3

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

4 Allocation of Resources

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Archiving

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Birgitta Andreassen (0000-0002-3778-4035)

5 Security

6 Ethical Aspects

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7 Other Issues

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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